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ABSTRACTS

- **15th International Conference** «Nuclear and Radiation Physics»
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- **8th CERN School** «Introduction to high-energy physics, accelerator technology and nuclear medicine»

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ISOTHERMAL DECAY ANALYSIS OF INTERMEDIATE TL PEAKS OF NANO- α -ALUMINA

Ahadov, A¹, Mammadov, S¹, Gurbanov, M¹, Abishov, A¹, Ahadova, A¹

¹Institute of Radiation Problems, Ministry of Science and Education

This work is a continuation of a thermoluminescence (TL) study of the behaviour of nano α -Al₂O₃ (40 nm) in the temperature range of 110 to 160°C to elucidate the kinetic mechanisms driving its TL response [1–4]. The isothermal decay curves were analyzed to determine the order of kinetics and activation energies of the TL peaks. The ln(I) vs. time plot revealed a nonlinearity starting at 140°C, indicating that the TL peaks do not follow first-order kinetics in this temperature region. Subsequent analysis confirmed that the TL data align with second-order kinetics, with a kinetic-order parameter of $b = 2.0$ providing the best linear fit.

Figure 1. Deconvolution of the 460 K TL glow peak of the irradiated (2,645 Gy) nano- α -Al₂O₃ with particle size of 40 nm into three peaks.

Further examination of the ln(slope) vs. 1/kT relationship revealed a composite structure in the TL response, characterized by three distinct linear sections. These sections correspond to activation energies of 0.6 ± 0.12 eV, 1.07 ± 0.25 eV, and 1.61 ± 0.47 eV, respectively, suggesting the presence of three different centers contributing to the dosimetric peak. To address the above behavior for nano-sized alumina, the main dosimetric peak was also deconvoluted into three peaks applying the Computerized Glow Curve Deconvolution (CGCD) procedure using GlowFit program (Fig. 1). The maximum temperatures of the three component glow peaks were found to be 425, 472 and 503 K. Correspondingly, the activation energies for these peaks were found to be 0.68 eV, 1.01 eV and 0.85 eV, while the corresponding frequency factors were calculated to be 5.10×10^6 , 3.45×10^{10} and 1.29×10^8 s⁻¹.

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